

Entrepreneurship Creative Projects as an Effort to Improve Interest in Entrepreneurship Students

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ABSTRACT, Entrepreneurship can be a solution in reducing poverty in Indonesia, especially if it is carried out in accordance with the principles of entrepreneurship. The latest models, forms and styles (trends) of entrepreneurship continue to change along with the progress of the times and technological sophistication so that being an entrepreneur does not have to be able to master the science of entrepreneurship. The informants of this study were students of the PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School. The results of the study explain that Implementation of creative entrepreneurial projects in PGRI 3 Vocational High School Malang has been going well in providing students' readiness for entrepreneurship. Implementation of creative and entrepreneurial projects through entrepreneurship learning for all students in grades X, XI and XII and integrated with various school activities

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurial Interests, Entrepreneurial Creative Projects, Hard Skills, Soft Skills

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurial boom conditions in Indonesia during 2018 have not skilled a substantial enlarge like different international locations in the world, prerequisites like this will have a have an effect on on the country's economic system which is constantly changing. Economic boom is additionally predicted to contract (republika.co.id, 2018). Other matters advised by the Minister of Cooperatives and MSMEs referred to that in line with the government's desire to realise Indonesia's imaginative and prescient in 2045, the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs continues to try to make bigger the quantity of entrepreneurs in Indonesia. These efforts have begun to endure fruit due to the fact in 2018, the ratio of entrepreneurs in Indonesia increased to extra than seven percent of the complete populace of Indonesia. (News Media, 2018). The phenomenon above shows that all factors must be concerned in growing the number of entrepreneurs in Indonesia. The crew that can be performed greater is the group of younger people. So that the segmentation of entrepreneurial activists have to be greater centered on strengthening theyoung people to open the widest area of entrepreneurship (Salami, 2020).

Entrepreneurship can be a answer in decreasing poverty in Indonesia, specifically if it is carried out in accordance with the concepts of entrepreneurship. The cutting-edge models, varieties and patterns (trends) of entrepreneurship continue to change alongside with the development of the instances and technological sophistication so that being an entrepreneur does now not have to be in a position to master entrepreneurship (hard skills), but extra than that one must additionally master gentle competencies as well. Previous research carried out via (Utomo, 2010; Diandra, 2019) defined that gentle capabilities in entrepreneurship play a position in increasing business effects (turnover). Lukman & Limgiani (2020) Education as phase of the formation of human civilization will routinely ride improvement and change, along with technological developments. Technological tendencies will also an increasing number of affect the existence of the world of schooling and scientific theories that are immediately related to technological know-how customers

Utomo (2010) also explains that smooth skills and the potential or abilities to relate to different human beings (people skills) have a slight difference and each can decide the success of an entrepreneur. Utomo (2010) mentioned in his lookup on smooth skills that the existence of skills or potential approves a character to compete in entering the world of work or the enterprise world. Interest is carefully related to attention, therefore pastime is a very decisive thing in each and every business. Interest is now not introduced from birth, however activity grows and develops according to the factors that have an effect on it (Wulandari, 2013). Broadly speaking, there are three factors that have an impact on interest, particularly environmental, psychological and physical. Environmental elements that have an impact on are additionally divided into 3 parts, specifically the

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family, faculty and community environment. One of them is the challenge of innovative entrepreneurship tasks and production units in schools. In previous studies that the family surroundings immediately influences the interest in entrepreneurship. (Wahyuningsih, 2018). This is in line with Tong, David and Liang's lookup (2011) which concluded that college students will be interested in becoming entrepreneurs if there is a want for achievement, family surroundings and subjective influence.

The Creative Entrepreneurship Project is targeted on entrepreneurial conduct as an empirical phenomenon that happens in the pupil environment. Yaskun, M & Sudarmiatin (2021) Entrepreneurial orientation is a characteristic and price held by way of entrepreneurs themselves, which are the nature of in no way giving up, taking risks, pace and flexibility. Based on a preliminary survey carried out by means of Agung Winarno, (2015) in countless vocational colleges in East Java Province, 18 schools unfold throughout the cities of Malang, Blitar, Kediri, Mojokerto, Jember and Banyuwangi. The implementation of the Entrepreneurship Creative Project gaining knowledge of that is taught in schools, so far has solely brought the theoretical concept of entrepreneurship yet to the stage of how to give the spirit to be an entrepreneur. The results of the find out about when adjusted to the state-of-the-art conditions have totally changed, because the Directorate of Vocational High Schools has made many efforts to improve the stipulations described in the research above. The SPW (School for Entrepreneurial Printing) software from 2018 to 2020 has been strolling until stage 4, as one answer to solve these problems.

Based on the above phenomena, it strengthens the researcher's want to habits research related to how to build students' entrepreneurial readiness in phrases of strengthening skills or expertise consisting of entrepreneurial abilities (hard skills) and smooth abilities from entrepreneurship (soft skills) originating from the household and college surroundings in this case the function of entrepreneurship creative task subjects and service production devices.

RIVIEW LITERATURE

Businessman

Entrepreneurs (entrepreneurs) are people who have the courage to take risks or are mentally independent without being overwhelmed by fear and anxiety to open a business on various occasions (Kasmir, 2010). Suherman (2010), which states that entrepreneurship is an entrepreneurial attitude and behavior that is innovative, anticipatory, initiative, risk-taking, and profit-oriented. Sar (2020) states that entrepreneurship is a form of business to create value through recognition of business opportunities, management or a systematic way of taking risks according to existing opportunities, and through communication skills to mobilize human, financial, or other resources to bring a product. or project until successful, Entrepreneurship is a mental and mental attitude that is always active to try to improve the results of his work in the sense of increasing one's income or attitudes, behavior, and abilities in handling businesses that lead to new ways of working, technology, and products. (Syaifuddin *et al.* 2015).

Skills or Entrepreneurship Skills

Skills is the ability to use reason, thoughts and ideas and creativity in doing, changing or making something more meaningful so as to produce a value from the work. In other words, skill is an ability to translate knowledge into practice so that the desired work result is achieved. (Suprpto, 2009). Chell (2013) states that skills are "Skills are not the same as abilities, the exercise of skill produces proficiency at tasks, whereas abilities are akin to more general traits". Skill or skill is not the same as ability, practice of skill or skill produces proficiency as a task, while ability is similar to more general traits.

Implementation of Entrepreneurial Creative Projects

According to UNCTAD (2008), the creative industry is defined as: (1) The cycle of creation, production, and distribution of goods and services that use creativity and intellectual capital as the main input (2) A series of knowledge-based activities that emphasize art that has the potential to provide income from trade and intellectual property rights (3) Consists of intellectual products or artistic services, both visible and invisible, with creative materials, economic value, and having a clear target market (4) The intersection between the arts, services, and industrial sectors (5) The realization of a dynamic new sector in world trade.

METHOD

Moleong (2017), while the data analysis uses inductive data analysis, with data collection more directly related to informants and researchers as key instruments. This study explores to reveal the external factors of students' family background and internal factors for the Creative Entrepreneurship Project as well as internal factors from the activities of the service production unit in the Entrepreneurial Printing School (SPW) SMK PGRI 3 Malang.

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The stages of research activities that will be carried out are (1) Data Collection (Collecting Data) (2) Data Condensation (Data Condensation) (3) Data Display (Data Display) (4) Conclusions Drawing. Informants in the research are class XI and class XII students who each have expertise in the field of Online Marketing Business expertise competencies.

RESEARCH RESULT

Initially the structure of the 2013 Curriculum for each high school and equivalent vocational school contained Craft and Entrepreneurship subjects that provided students with a basic understanding of entrepreneurship skills. The government has launched an Entrepreneurship program in PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School Equivalent which is expected to encourage students to be creative and independent, and start to be moved and dare to open their own businesses. Until then the 2013 Curriculum was revised and instructed to change the subjects of Entrepreneurship and Crafts into Creative Products and Entrepreneurship, this change did not only occur in the name, but also in the number of hours of lessons and the learning system. Giving entrepreneurship subjects is one of the government's efforts in fostering student entrepreneurship interest.

For Vocational High Schools designated as Entrepreneurial Printing Schools, the entrepreneurship program development model is expected to be able to disseminate it to surrounding schools and develop activities into creative entrepreneurship. The formation of entrepreneurial individuals is an indicator of the successful implementation of entrepreneurship programs in vocational schools. The success of the creative entrepreneurship project program in Vocational Schools can be seen through the performance results that have been achieved by the school including including a school environment that has an entrepreneurial feel, learning that integrates design thinking models in the creative process of problem solving, students have entrepreneurial character and behavior, and students who are able to become entrepreneurs. independently or in groups.

In this case, the implementation of effective entrepreneurship creative project learning in schools will be able to help encourage students to be more prepared for entrepreneurship and have the knowledge to start a business. PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School itself has implemented creative entrepreneurial projects through entrepreneurship learning which is integrated with learning and other school activities. The subject of creative entrepreneurship projects at PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School is included in the revised curriculum for entrepreneurship education in schools that has been regulated by the Government and has developed a program of activities by the school. All students in grades X, XI and XII receive this entrepreneurship lesson to support business interests and improve their entrepreneurial abilities.

"Yes, I am a class XI student with online marketing business skills competency, and I have received subjects in the creative entrepreneurship project program at school. The learning is not only formal, but also integrated with other school activities such as extracurricular activities and self-development."

Similar to the statement made by Vega, a class XII student of Marketing Online Business skill competence in the results of his interview as follows,

"...all students can learn entrepreneurship, including for class XII as well, the name is creative and entrepreneurial products. For class XII, what is taught is already in the marketing and business development stages. For class X, it's still a proposal or looking for business opportunities, after that product creation and then sales and marketing. It could also be just a drop shipper or wholesaler, or buying a friend's or senior's product and then selling it, that's basically it"

The implementation of creative and entrepreneurial projects through entrepreneurship learning for all students in grades X, XI and XII at SMK PGRI 3 Malang was also explained by one of the entrepreneurship subject teachers as follows,

"Entrepreneurship education in any school, there is something structured from the government and at PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School, grades X, XI, and XII use the revised K13 curriculum which is applied through the subjects of creative products and entrepreneurship, as well as other subjects that are instilled in values. entrepreneurial value in it. So this entrepreneurship is implemented through various activities, the first being integrated in subjects, in extracurricular activities, activities held by schools such as exhibition activities per department and so on, also through skills programs in local content.."

Based on the interviews above, it shows that learning creative entrepreneurship projects in schools is integrated with various school activities and has been given to all students in grades X, XI and XII. Core competencies and basic competencies in the subject of Creative Products and Entrepreneurship require students to make a product, so that the learning model that teachers feel is the most appropriate is project-based learning. By doing a lot of direct practice, students will more easily understand the material and can apply it directly. In this case, the output of project-based learning is that students are able to create products or have their own business and sell their products.

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"Yes, during the creative product and entrepreneurship lesson, we were all told to be able to create our own business projects, so there are products that are produced and then sold to buyers, whether it's in the form of handicrafts, food products, or finished goods that are resold."

Putri also conveyed the same thing in the results of her interview as follows,

"The goal of every entrepreneurship lesson is that we always emphasize to be able to sell our own products, there are business projects that we run from the early 10th grade to the 12th grade later. The point is that we evaluate the output from how we can have our own business, so we can experience firsthand how an entrepreneur works."

In addition, the scope of the subject matter for creative products and entrepreneurship for secondary school education generally includes crafts, cultivation and processing, while in vocational high schools it is adjusted to the potential of schools and the local area. This was conveyed by one of the entrepreneurship subject teachers as follows,

"The entrepreneurship materials provided are grouped into 3, namely there are crafts (eg class 1 waste crafts, class 2 recycling crafts and so on), plant cultivation (hydroponic plant cultivation), and then processing (such as fruit juice but not for all fruits). And there is also the addition of vocational reinforcement for each student for vocational high schools that are tailored to the potential of the school and the local area."

Furthermore, several skills developed in the creative and entrepreneurial project implementation program carried out at PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School include hard skills and soft skills. The first is hard skills in opening up business opportunities as outlined in a business plan or business proposal. In this case, students are asked to make an initial draft of a business proposal. This is as conveyed by Nanda in the results of his interview as follows,

"Students of class XI in particular were asked to make an analysis of business opportunities. So at the beginning of the lesson we were told to make an initial business plan that we will make in the future in the form of a business proposal, so that the form of business continues to be the product that we want to sell or the market for our consumers, namely anyone. In that plan, the analysis of market opportunities is done by observing directly in places that have business opportunities, it can also be via the internet to see what opportunities around here there are opportunities that can be developed into businesses."

Second, hard skills in marketing the business they are starting. Marketing techniques in sales that are taught to students, are more directed to online marketing strategies and not conventional seeing the interest in using online buying and selling which has greater opportunities. This is as conveyed by Putri in the results of her interview as follows,

"When you reach class XII, what is taught is already in the marketing department, if we focus more on online marketing, we are directed how to attract consumers via online, profit and how to continue to carry out various attractive promotional strategies so that people are interested in buying our products."

Third, soft skills in communicating with potential customers and consumers who buy their products by offering their products persuasively. Students are taught how to communicate with consumers verbally and non-verbally to maintain good relations with consumers. This is as conveyed by Nanda in the results of his interview as follows,

"Regarding communication, it's more about business communication, we are also taught how to market products verbally to customers, so for example, a customer asks via DM about our product. How polite and proper to customers is, how to negotiate price tricks, all are taught."

Fourth, soft skills in leading to influence a group to achieve company goals. In this case students are taught indirectly through group learning by forming mutual cooperation in running a business. This is as conveyed by Ega in the results of his interview as follows,

"Leadership may be more when we form a group of how many people then we are judged on how we work together in running a business, it's more about teamwork."

Fifth, soft skills in time management or work discipline by doing things that should be done at the right time and really respecting time. In this case, students are taught about time discipline through collecting each task on time according to the specified schedule, carrying out the responsibilities given and being honest in every task that is done. This is as conveyed by Vega in the results of his interview as follows,

"Yes, every task we do is always given a deadline by the teacher, he said so we can be disciplined to be entrepreneurs, so we can manage time so we don't get stuck. By submitting assignments on time we show we can fulfill our responsibilities."

Furthermore, the success of implementing creative products and entrepreneurship lessons itself can be seen from the achievement of goals, namely soft skills and hard skills that have been successfully instilled in students to form an entrepreneurial spirit. In terms of hard skills, students must be able to transform their abilities through activities such as making

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a product. Meanwhile, in terms of soft skills, a student must be able to express creative ideas, have good cooperation, and be disciplined. In the implementation of creative products and entrepreneurship lessons at PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School, it is known that most students already have sufficient soft skills and hard skills in entrepreneurship and have independent business products that are still running today.

"This creative and entrepreneurial project program is held to teach students how to make products, continue to sell them. Which in essence is how students are entrepreneurship. And from what I have noticed, most of the students have shown their entrepreneurial abilities well, they already have good hard skills and good soft skills. Many interesting business ideas were put forward by the students, and I really appreciate the success of these students, and I hope that the business they have built can continue to run and grow to be even bigger."

The success of students in producing their own business products is also evident from the results of the interview with the informant, namely Nanda as a class XI student in the following interview,

"The business that I run is called Corner.id, the type is Fashion.... From the business that I run, I can buy my own necessities including cellphones, and my sister's school, I also help to pay for it from school needs to paying school fees."

In management science related to customer management, because this management is very important, according to Buttle (2007) Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a core strategy in business that integrates internal processes and functions with all external networks to create and realize value to target consumers on a profit basis". Meanwhile, according to Temporal and Troot (2002) argue that "CRM is essentially a collaboration with every consumer who is able to create conditions that do not harm either party. Then according to Kotler & Keller (2009) "Customer Relationship Management is the process of managing detailed information about each customer and carefully managing all customer "touch points" in order to maximize customer loyalty". The point is how to build customer loyalty to the products we make, continue to strive to motivate customers, and minimize the notion that the company is no longer product-oriented (product-oriented) but has been customer-oriented (customer-oriented). obtained in the implementation of Creative Entrepreneurship Projects subjects. As stated by Sasnanita as follows:

" Mr. Fathi taught me how to do a market survey, so that I know what my customers' needs are, because this is important for a business like me that is based on pre-orders, if I don't know the customer's needs and I make production based on most then maybe many people the one who died is me, that means no more messages to me"

So the importance of this Creative Entrepreneurship Projects subject with a content that really introduces, understands and explores the management science of a business organization, as conveyed by Putri as follows:

"..I know this subject, such as the development of the KWU subject that I have received, the difference is that this subject understands me better to do business and strengthen the business that I have run, Pak Gunawan teaches the calculation which we think is difficult at first glance , but if it is matched with my business or the business run by friends, the calculation makes sense, so it is very important that such knowledge is taught to students, so that students understand how to calculate their business well."

Meanwhile, Nanda said that this Creative Entrepreneurship Projects subject could create a special entity or series from his business, not the same as those of his friends, so that it was more salable than others, as Nanda conveyed in the results of his interview as follows:

"...if I, Mrs. Lilik, teaches making odd numbers when we sell goods or services, and not all friends do that, but I remember very well what Mrs. Lilik said in the PKK subject, so I was more interested and I proved it, what I did was successful, it means that lessons like this are needed for our minimal knowledge, I hope Mrs. Lilik provides management knowledge that is more than that"

Based on the results of the interviews above, it can be concluded that the implementation of creative entrepreneurial projects at PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School has gone well in providing students' readiness for entrepreneurship, a more modern scientific management approach with digital technology or modern stalls is a basic need and an indispensable need. The implementation of creative and entrepreneurial projects through entrepreneurship learning for all students in grades X, XI and XII and integrated with various school activities. The scope of the subject matter includes crafts, cultivation and processing, as well as in vocational high schools adapted to the potential of the school and the local area. The skills developed include hard skills which include opening up business opportunities as outlined in business proposals and marketing strategies, soft skills which include communication, leadership and collaboration skills, and time management in work discipline. The success of implementing creative entrepreneurial projects is evident from that most of the students assessed have sufficient soft skills and hard skills in entrepreneurship, and have independent business products that are still running today.

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DISCUSSION

Based on the results of interviews in the research above, it is strengthened for student development, namely the internal side in the implementation of the Entrepreneurial Printing School, namely in the Creative Entrepreneurship Projects subject, as illustrated in the slice chart below.

Figure 1. Creative Project Research Results

School involvement in implementing the achievement of implementation of preparing students for entrepreneurship actually plays an important role in addition to family external factors, so that the existing internal factors are carried out optimally and well, planned, measured, evaluated periodically and continuously improved. At PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School the implementation of internal factors which include the implementation Creative Entrepreneurship Projects subjects with a touch of management and business knowledge to strengthen the value of the project that will be made by students whether it has met market needs (based on market needs) or based on the results obtained (*turnover*) students, becomes a measure of success in preparing students for entrepreneurship. Scientific strengthening of student projects (assignments) based on careful planning, both in formulations such as a business plan, making a business model canvas, making cash flow, building an online stall, or looking for a marketplace with an online platform, which uses management analysis, organizing potential potential strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats as well as capital and human resources in this case the students concerned, because they are trained to become leaders and lead, and analyze the results of work in the acquisition of turnover conveyed to the maximum by the accompanying teacher to all students. So that it raises creativity to strengthen new products, make packaging or change existing products to maximize their appearance or product quality according to the market.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of creative entrepreneurship projects at PGRI 3 Malang Vocational High School Malang has gone well in providing students' readiness for entrepreneurship. The implementation of creative and entrepreneurial projects through entrepreneurship learning for all students in grades X, XI and XII and integrated with various school activities. The scope of the subject matter includes crafts, cultivation and processing, as well as in vocational high schools adapted to the potential of the school and the local area. The skills developed include hard skills which include opening up business opportunities as outlined in business proposals and marketing strategies, soft skills which include communication, leadership and collaboration skills, and time management in work discipline.

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